

SmartKit: an Architecture for Modelling Complex Industrial Tasks

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Abstract—The interest in collaborative robotics applications keeps increasing with the advancing of the years. Such growth is due to the robot’s flexibility in the production line and to the interactions that may happen with the human partner. However, human-robot collaboration is far from being adopted in practice, especially for complex industrial applications such as assembly tasks. This work formalises an architecture that models human and robot workflows and synchronises their activities, spots errors during the human task execution, and notifies the operator that something unexpected happened. The system has then been tested in an industrial collaborative assembly operation.

Index Terms—Semantics for robots, Human-robot collaboration, Architecture for smart robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of Industry 4.0, Small Medium Enterprises had to shift their production from mass volumes to mass customisation. Such change requires flexible production lines which are more and more populated by collaborative robots together with humans [1]. In order to be considered a flexible tool, cobots will need to cope with different situations depending on the understanding of the environment around them and be prepared to face possible unexpected scenarios like human errors. In this framework, the main challenge is to devise architectures that can model and monitor the workflow, with the goal of spotting robotics or human errors. Several works exist that exploit the current world state to model and notify the operator about possible errors, like for example [2] or [3]. These methods, however, while being robust, require data collection and labelling procedures, which can be a tedious and time-consuming task, if the production line undergoes frequent modifications due to production changes.

The present work contributes to making the robot a flexible tool and integrating human-robot collaboration, with an innovative architecture called *SmartKit* that relies on the *Digital Twins* concept to model the task workflow, making it more reliable and less error-prone. The architecture puts together a digitalised version of the work cell (composed of the robot, the human and other tools) and a PLC-like logic that represents the modelled task and sends signals to the robot or the human depending on the environment state. In light of the above, the proposed solution allows error detection and correction by the

smart architecture [4], increasing human-robot synchronization and ensuring a more fluent and seamless collaboration.

II. ARCHITECTURE STRUCTURE

This Section introduces *SmartKit*: a control architecture, that once the task has been designed, allows the execution of a collaborative task.

The proposed architecture is represented in Fig. 1 and comprises four major components: The block named *World model* contains a digital representation of the whole workspace. In particular, the *Digital Twin* of each component of the workspace is represented and its parameters are constantly updated through measurements coming from the robot (e.g. to update the position of each robot joint), cameras (e.g. to locate objects or humans) or GPIO boards that can read analogue signals. The block named *Signal register* contains a set of first order logic functions (also known as predicates) that output true or false depending on the predicates implementation and the state of each *Digital Twin* that composes the *World model*. An example could be *IsObjectInHand(Right Hand, Screw-driver)* which outputs true/false after querying the *Digital Twins* of the robot and the object present in the *World model*; The block named *Boolean expression(s)* allows a combination of the previously explained predicates through first order logic operators such as *and*, *or* and *not*. Such predicates combination grants the robot to have a more comprehensive knowledge of the environment allowing to model more complex human-robot interactions; The block named *Control logic* contains the rules needed for the design of the workflows of the human and the robot for the collaborative task. In particular, this part exploits an SFC style programming language to represent the collaborative task. Indeed, each state describes a phase of the task and each of these sends to the robot the appropriate command to be executed. The passage from one state to the other happens only if particular conditions coming from the field are satisfied or not.

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE USE CASE

The proposed architecture has been used to design the workflow of a collaborative assembly of a rear motorbike

Fig. 1: Block diagram of the proposed architecture for the development of human-robot collaborative applications.

brake. The system supervises the worker’s operations (like fastening, screwing, etc.) assuming he/she employs standard working tools. During the task execution, it guarantees a smooth collaboration between the robot and the human engaged in the workspace since it synchronises the two agents to work in the collaborative area: the switch from one worker to the other is performed without the need of gesture recognition or the press of physical buttons that may distract the operator. The accompanying video ¹ shows the two agents collaborating.

Fig. 2: In the figure the operator is working on the oil tank assembly, and the robot is inserting a washer on a screw. Collaborative volumes V_1 and V_2 are also highlighted.

The brake is composed of three parts: the oil tank, the pump, and the caliper. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 2. The workflow is structured as follows: when the operator deposits the pallet containing the brake, the collaborative dual-arm robot, YuMi by ABB, performs the assembly of the oil tube connection, manipulating the tube and inserting in its connector a screw and two washers. After that, it pre-tightens the tube connector to the pump. At the same time, the worker is responsible for assembling the oil tank. Once the robot has pre-tightened the oil tube to the pump, it waits for the worker to finish the tightening operation with the pneumatic ratchet. As soon as the operator finishes the tightening operation and exits the collaborative area, the robot resumes its work. The same procedure is performed to assemble and pre-tight the connector of the oil tube with the caliper. Finally, the

operator needs to tighten with the pneumatic ratchet the tube connector to the caliper.

The workflow has been designed with an SFC logic which describes the phases that composed the human parts of the task and the robotic ones. The current state of the SFC represents a particular phase of the workflow: it is then possible to synchronize the human-robot actions communicating to the robot when to start an assembly task and when to wait for the worker to finish his/her task in the collaborative area. These wait commands tie the human activity recognition with the robot’s actions, allowing a smooth and natural collaboration. Two volumes, V_1 and V_2 of Fig. 2 represent the collaborative areas where the pallet must be positioned and where the tightening operations must be performed. In particular, volume V_1 is used to begin the operation: the robot starts moving only when the volume is considered occupied. Volume V_2 is exploited to check if the tightening operations are correctly performed: the system checks if the operator’s hands are inside the volume V_2 , holding the proper tool at the right state of the workflow.

To conclude, the conditions characterising the SFC transitions are composed of a combination of predicates that create a complex condition, such as “using the ratchet in V_2 ” that merges the knowledge of human-object interaction with the volume V_2 occupancy.

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¹<https://youtu.be/RUxv9PGUtJQ>